

CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL CONDITION OF THE BROAD FASCIA OF THE FEMUR IN PATIENTS WHO UNDERWENT COVID-19

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Annotation. Post covid syndrome is manifested by long-term pathological complications, among which a significant proportion of patients' complaints are joint pains. Regardless of the severity of the disease caused by COVID-19, those who have been ill are diagnosed with disorders of the type of reactive arthritis. Coronavirus infection became a trigger for existing joint diseases, in particular, aseptic necrosis of the femoral head (ANGBC).

According to the English Registry, the incidence of osteonecrosis in the UK population ranges from 1.4 to 3.0 per 100,000 population. At the same time, in 75.9% of cases, the femoral head is affected. In the United States, the number of patients with ANGB (NFH) ranges from 300,000 to 600,000. At the same time, the number of detected primary cases of osteonecrosis ranges from 10 to 20 thousand per year. In Japan, the incidence rate is 1.9 per 100,000 population.

Keywords : broad fascia, post covid syndrome, complications.

The purpose of the study. To study the structural characteristics of the broad fascia of the hip in patients with ANGB and develop optimal approaches to their rehabilitation.

The object of the study. Studies were conducted on 150 patients who will be operated on. In accordance with the objectives of the study, all the observed were divided into 2 comparable groups.

Research methods.

During the study, we were contacted by 150 patients who underwent this procedure, 63 of them women and 87 men. The average age of patients is 22 years (from 15 years to 35 years).

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